

Development and validation of analytical procedure for analysis of polyvinylpyrrolidone in tablets containing metformin hydrochloride and pioglitazone hydrochloride

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Abstract

Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) is a common excipient in pharmaceutical formulations due to its inert, biocompatible, and multifunctional properties. However, its presence can impact drug release. This study aims to optimize the analysis method for determining PVP concentration in tablets containing a combination of metformin hydrochloride and pioglitazone hydrochloride. The research involved optimizing stationary and mobile phases using HPLC, detector optimization, sample preparation, and stability testing. Validation followed ICH guidelines, covering system suitability, specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, detection and quantitation limits, range, and robustness. HPLC with a reverse-phase column, UV detector, and SEC column with RID detector were utilized. The optimized HPLC method with sodium nitrate and acetonitrile mobile phase (80:20) provided accurate results. PVP content in tested tablets was 3.91% and 4.12% by weight for PioMix and ActMet, respectively. The method demonstrated stability and robustness under deliberate changes. In conclusion, the validated HPLC method offers a reliable means for PVP analysis in tablets containing metformin HCl and pioglitazone HCl, which is suitable for quality control and regulatory compliance.

Keywords

polyvinylpyrrolidone, excipient, validation, SEC, metformin, pioglitazone

Introduction

Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), commonly known as Povidone, is a synthetic polymer synthesized through the radical polymerization of the monomer N-vinylpyrrolidone (Haaf et al. 1985). PVP is nontoxic, non-ionic, inert, temperature-resistant, pH-stable, biocompatible, and has a complex affinity for hydrophilic and

hydrophobic drugs (Kurakula and Koteswara Rao 2020). The different molecular weights of PVP are distinguished by distinct K-values (Schwarz 1990). Fig. 1 shows the structure of povidone.

Applications of PVP include pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, food, adhesives, polymers, and textiles (Haaf et al. 1985; Devi et al. 2012; Ibrahim et al. 2019; van der Merwe et al. 2020; Ghyadh and Al-Khedairy 2023).

Figure 1. Chemical structure of polyvinylpyrrolidone.

PVP is important in oral formulations due to its multifunctional properties. It acts as a solubilizer, stabilizer, binder, lubricant, and crystallization inhibitor, enhancing the bioavailability and solubility of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs). PVP can interact with active ingredients in the final dosage form. For example, PVP can enhance the inclusion complex formation between APIs and cyclodextrins, influencing drug solubility and stability. Additionally, PVP can inhibit chemical degradation of certain APIs in solid-state formulations. The quantification of PVP in tablets is important because PVP can affect the stability and bioavailability of the active ingredients. Accurate quantification ensures that the optimal amount of PVP is used to achieve the desired effects without compromising the efficacy of the formulation (Bejaoui et al. 2021).

Numerous chromatographic techniques have been documented in the literature to assess PVP (polyvinylpyrrolidone), either for qualitative determination of the polymer's molecular weight range or quantitative analysis of formulations and products such as, High Performance Liquid Chromatography and Size Exclusion Chromatography (SEC). (Jones et al. 2004; Ericsson 2010; Tavlarakis et al. 2011).

Several studies have shown adequate separation of PVP in both reverse-phase and SEC conditions. A reverse-phase HPLC method with UV detection was employed to separate and quantify PVP K-15 from pharmaceutical formulations. The assay used a C18 HPLC column in combination with an 80:20 propanol: deionized water containing 0.01% TFA mobile phase (Jones et al. 2004).

Size exclusion chromatography with UV detection has been validated to determine the total PVP content in eye drop solutions. The study used a TSKgel G1000PW column, 7.5 mm i.d. \times 30 cm, 12 μ m filled with hydrophilic polymer material. The column temperature was set at 50 $^{\circ}$ C, with a mobile phase of sodium acetate: methanol = 80:20, and UV detection at a wavelength of 220 nm (Tavlarakis et al. 2011).

The separation of PVP using the SEC system was also reported in a study (Ericsson 2010) that analyzed PVP from urinary catheter extraction solutions using a PL-aquagel-OH column, an RID detector, and a mobile phase consisting of pure water, 0.1M sodium nitrate, 0.1M sodium chloride, and a mixture of pure water and methanol at

50:50. It was found that the mobile phase of 0.1M sodium nitrate was most suitable for separating PVP.

The Office of Generic Drugs has ensured the high quality of generic products based upon two requirements: pharmaceutical equivalence and bioequivalence to the reference listed drug (RLD) (Raw et al. 2011). Bioavailability and bioequivalence assessments are integral parts of the drug product approval process (Oner and Polli 2018).

Thus, this study aims to develop and validate a method for analyzing PVP in the tablet formulations to assist in developing generic products.

Methodology

Chromatographic condition

All chemicals and reagents used are of chromatographic purity. Polyvinylpyrrolidone reference standards and a ready calibration set of polyethylene glycol/polyethylene oxide were obtained from Sigma Aldrich. Tablet forms containing metformin hydrochloride 500 mg and pioglitazone hydrochloride equivalent to pioglitazone 15 mg are produced in the R&D laboratory of PT. Kalbe Farma, Tbk, and the reference products are commercially available. An Agilent HPLC 1260 Infinity II LC system, consisting of the following components: 1260 Infinity Quaternary Pump, 1260 Infinity Degasser, and refractive index detector, was used. The separation was performed on an Ultrahydrogel 120 column (300 \times 7.8 mm, particle size 6 μ m, pore size 120 Å) under size exclusion chromatographic conditions. The mobile phase is an 80:20% v/v mixture of 0.1M sodium nitrate in purified water: acetonitrile. The mobile phase was filtered through a 0.45 μ m PVDF membrane filter and degassed using an ultrasonic bath for about 15 minutes. Sample solutions were also filtered using a 0.45 μ m PVDF membrane filter. The working conditions are as follows: flow rate of 0.6 mL/min, column temperature of 30 $^{\circ}$ C, injection volume of 20 μ L, and total retention time of 30 minutes.

Preparation of stock and working standard

A stock solution of PVP 30 was prepared at a 25 mg/mL concentration in purified water. The stock solution was diluted to produce working standard solutions with a 2.5 mg/mL concentration. Calibration standards were prepared by diluting the stock solution with purified water to obtain a concentration range from 0.25 mg/mL to 3.75 mg/mL. Ready calibration Standard polyethylene glycol/polyethylene oxide was directly injected into the system without further dilution.

Preparation of synthetic mixture or placebo

A bulk mixture without PVP was prepared per tablet formula using metformin HCl and pioglitazone HCl. Common

excipients used in tablet formulations were added to this mixture, including glycerine, croscarmellose sodium, microcrystalline cellulose, magnesium stearate, and purified water.

Preparation of pharmaceutical tablet

Pharmaceutical tablets were prepared using the wet granulation method, consisting of metformin HCl, pioglitazone HCl, and all excipients, compressed with an average weight of 585 mg per tablet.

Preparation of sample solutions

Ten tablets, each containing metformin hydrochloride 500 mg and pioglitazone hydrochloride equivalent to pioglitazone 15 mg, were weighed and then powdered. The amount equivalent to the average weight of 1 tablet was then transferred to a 10 mL volumetric flask and dissolved with about 8 mL of purified water. The samples were allowed to dissolve in water for 3 hours and then made up with purified water. After that, the solution was filtered through a PVDF 0.45 μm membrane filter and analyzed.

HPLC method validation

The HPLC-SEC method for quantifying PVP 30 in pharmaceutical tablets was validated in terms of system suitability, specificity, linearity, limit of detection (LOD), and limit of quantification (LOQ), accuracy, precision, and robustness by the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines.

System suitability

The system suitability test was evaluated by injecting a working standard solution into the chromatographic system for six replicate injections. System fit characteristics such as tailing factor, retention time, resolution, theoretical plates, and analyte peak responses were assessed.

Specificity

The objective of the specificity testing was to demonstrate that the main peaks of the analyte could be differentiated from those of the sample matrix and any associated peaks. A placebo solution was also injected into the chromatographic system to ensure no interference from the sample matrix. The spiked substance (PVP 30) was used in the placebo samples to evaluate the specificity of detecting and differentiating PVP 30 from other substances.

Linearity

Linearity was assessed by examining calibration standards (ranging from 0.25 mg/mL to 3.75 mg/mL) at 7 different concentrations in 3 replicates. Calibration curves were generated by linear regression, plotting the PVP 30 concentrations (x) as the abscissa and the peak response (y) as the ordinate.

Limits of detection and quantification

The detection or quantification limits are the minimum concentrations at which the analyte can be reliably detected or quantitated. A signal-to-noise ratio of 3:1 is generally considered acceptable for estimating the detection limit. A ratio of at least 10:1 is considered acceptable for the quantification limit. The detection limit was defined using the equation $\text{LOD} = 3.3 \sigma/S$, and the limit of quantitation with the equation $\text{LOQ} = 10 \sigma/S$, where σ is the standard deviation of the responses, and S is the slope of the calibration curve.

Accuracy

The method's accuracy was measured at three concentrations of the sample solutions (70%, 100%, and 130%) using nine determinations (three replicates of each concentration). Three different levels of standard solutions (1.75, 2.50, and 3.25 mg/mL) were spiked into the placebo. Percent recoveries were calculated by comparing the measured amount of those standards with the amount added.

Precision

The method's precision was assessed in terms of repeatability and intermediate precision. Repeatability was evaluated through six determinations at 100% of the test concentration, while intermediate precision was investigated using authentic homogeneous samples performed on three different days and by three different analysts. Precisions were determined by calculating the relative standard deviation percentage (% RSD) on the same day and on three different days, respectively.

Robustness

The method's robustness was assessed by intentionally modifying the chromatographic conditions, such as the percentage of the organic phase, flow rate, and column temperature, by slightly increasing or decreasing them. Each parameter was changed, one at a time. System suitability and sample runs were conducted using unchanged and modified method parameters. Furthermore, standard and sample solutions were stored at room temperature and analyzed at initial, 24, 48, and 72-hour intervals to assess sample stability. The solutions were tested against a freshly prepared standard at each time point.

Result and discussion

Optimization of chromatographic conditions

The primary objective of chromatographic optimization is to achieve elution with an acceptable retention time, peak symmetry, high selectivity, and accuracy of the PVP

peak in tablet formulations. The parameters assessed and optimized in this study include the column type, detector type, percentage of organic modifier, aqueous phase concentration, mobile phase additives, and flow rate. Several system conditions were examined for the optimization of chromatographic conditions, including reverse-phase and size-exclusion chromatography systems with ultraviolet (UV) detectors and refractive index (RI) detectors.

The studies employed a reverse-phase system with a C18 column and a mobile phase consisting of propanol and 0.01% tetrahydrofuran in ratios of 80:20, 50:50, and 20:80. The UV detection wavelength was set to 243 nm. Ultrahydrogel 120 and 1000 columns were used in SEC studies, with mobile phases of 0.1M sodium nitrate and acetonitrile in ratios of 80:20, 85:15, 90:10, and 95:5. An RI detector was employed in this system. Other salts, such as sodium chloride and ammonium acetate, were also examined. The flow rate and column temperature were studied within the limits specified in the column's instruction manual.

In this study, several types of PVP were injected into the chromatographic system, and the separation of the target analytes was observed. PVP-10, PVP-25, PVP-30, PVP-40, and PVP-90 were chosen considering that these types are commonly used in tablet formulations, as referenced in the FDA Inactive Ingredient Search for Approved Drug Products. The optimal conditions were obtained with the SEC system using the Ultrahydrogel 120 column, an RI detector, and a mobile phase of sodium nitrate: acetonitrile (80:20) with a 0.6 mL/minute flow rate. The injection volume and column temperature were set at 20 μ L and 30 $^{\circ}$ C, respectively.

Calibrations were performed using narrow polyethylene glycol/oxide (PEG/PEO) standards to identify the type of PVP that might be used in the reference tablet. PEG/PEO-ready calibration standards, obtained from Sigma Aldrich and Polymer Laboratories with molecular weights ranging from 238 to 1,180,000 Da, were used to create calibration curves. These standards were directly injected into the system. The oxides cover the higher molecular weight range, while the glycols cover the lower molecular weight range. Calibration curves plotting retention volume against the logarithm of molecular weight were created. Subsequently, the retention volume of PVP detected in the tablet solutions was plotted on these curves to estimate the molecular weight of the PVP. In this study, an SEC column of Ultrahydrogel 1000 was coupled with Ultrahydrogel 120 to facilitate separating a wide range of molecular weights in the PEG/PEO standard calibration. Coupling columns of different pore sizes gives SEC a tremendous dynamic range, separating within a single experiment across orders of magnitude in molar mass (Striegel 2022).

PEG/PEO calibration curves and chromatograms were presented in Figs 2, 3 and Tables 1, 2. The molecules' size and shape mainly govern the separation process in size-exclusion chromatography. As the sample is injected into the column, it undergoes a size-based separation, with larger molecules eluting first and smaller molecules eluting later (Soni 2023).

Table 1. Retention volume and molecular weight of PEG/PEO calibration standards.

Standard BCCJ3787	Material	Retention volume (mL)	Mw	log Mw	Peak responses (nRI)
STD Black	PEO-1180000	11.0016	1,180,000	6.072	166,661
STD Blue	PEO-504000	11.8050	50,4000	5.702	357,715
STD Yellow	PEO-217000	12.5682	21,7000	5.336	276,703
STD Black	PEO-99000	13.2216	99,000	4.996	388,053
STD Blue	PEO-42700	14.0346	42,700	4.630	375,787
STD Yellow	PEO-18600	14.6772	18,600	4.270	343,998
STD Black	PEG-6530	15.3480	6,530	3.815	369,366
STD Yellow	PEG-2130	16.3590	2,130	3.328	373,199
STD Blue	PEG-599	17.5608	599	2.777	385,644
STD Yellow	PEG-238	18.6516	238	2.377	352,398

*STD: standard

Table 2. Molecular weight estimation of PVP in material and tablets.

Material	Retention volume (mL)	Log Mw	Estimated Mw	Peak response (nRI)
PVP 10	15.4578	3.864	7,302	442,098
PVP 25	15.0744	4.055	11,346	1,050,046
PVP 30	14.7804	4.202	15,908	1,184,190
PVP 40	14.8326	4.176	14,982	1,172,750
PVP 90	12.1752	5.503	317,790	1,304,290
PVP 360	12.1146	5.533	340,715	1,258,958
PVP 1300	12.2748	5.453	283,413	1,336,510
PVP in PioMix tablet ^a	14.9118	4.137	13,678	593,259
PVP in ActMet tablet ^b	14.7042	4.240	17,365	1,201,316

^aTest product

^bReference product

Figure 2. PEG/PEO calibration curves.

Based on the estimated molecular weights obtained from calibration plotting to the PEG/PEO narrow calibration standards, the PVP used in PioMix and ActMet Met Tablets has molecular weights of approximately 13,678 and 17,365, respectively. These molecular weights are close to those of PVP-30 and PVP-40. Based on this finding, further quantitative determination of PVP in the tablet formulations was conducted using PVP-30 as the reference standard, considering that PVP-30 is the most common PVP used in tablet formulations.

Figure 3. Chromatogram of PEG/PEO standards. **a.** Standard Black (PEO-1180000, PEO-99000, and PEG-6530); **b.** Standard Blue (PEO-504000, PEO-42700, and PEG-599); **c.** Standard Yellow (PEO-217000, PEO-18600, PEG-2130, and PEG-238).

System suitability

The system suitability tests represent an integral part of the analytical procedure and are used to ensure adequate performance of the chromatographic system (United States Pharmacopeia 2023). Under optimized chromatographic conditions, system suitability parameters, such as column efficiency expressed by the number of theoretical plates (N), tailing factor (T), resolution (R), and repeatability (RSD of peak response and retention time), were evaluated and listed in Table 3. The calculated parameters were satisfactory and suggested the method's high efficiency for determining PVP 30.

Table 3. HPLC system suitability parameters for the determination of PVP 30 using the proposed method.

Retention time (t_r)	No. of theoretical plates (N)	Tailing factor (T)	% RSD of peak responses	Resolution (Rs)
9.113 ± 0.001	2900	1.4	0.1% (n = 6)	5.0

Specificity

From the experiments performed, a complete separation of PVP 30 from the diluent and sample matrix was obtained, as shown in Fig. 4. The PVP peak has a clear baseline separation and is well separated from other components in the placebo. The retention time is sufficient for the analyte separation, and there is no overlap between peaks obtained from resolution data, indicating a reliable system.

Linearity, limit of detection, and limit of quantification

Linearity was determined for a standard of PVP 30 over a concentration range of 0.25 mg/mL to 3.75 mg/mL. The calibration curve was created using seven points covering seven different test compound concentrations within the specified concentration range. Linear regression was employed to process the calibration data. Then, the limit of detection and quantification was defined using the equation: $LOD = 3.3 \sigma/S$ and $LOQ = 10 \sigma/S$, where σ is the standard deviation of the responses, and S is the slope of the calibration curve.

The linearity parameters, such as the correlation coefficient, intercept, slope, and standard deviation of the residuals for the calibration data and concentration range, are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Linearity data obtained for PVP 30.

Parameter	Results
Linearity range (mg/mL) ^a	0.25–3.75
Slope	307161
Intercept	0
Correlation coefficient (R^2)	0.9999
Standard deviation of the residuals $S_{y/x}$	0.5573
LOD (mg/mL)	0.0355
LOQ (mg/mL)	0.1075

^aAt 0.25, 0.75, 1.25, 1.75, 2.50, 3.25, and 3.75 mg/mL concentration levels, with average of three determinations.

Figure 4. Chromatogram specificity of PVP 30. **a.** Diluent; **b.** PVP 30 standard solution; **c.** Placebo solution; **d.** Placebo spiked with PVP 30 solution, and **e.** Formulation sample solution.

Accuracy

Recovery studies were conducted to verify the accuracy of the developed method. To pre-analyze the tablet solution, a specific concentration of PVP standard (70%, 100%, and 130%) was added, and then its recovery was determined. The statistical validation of the recovery studies is presented in Table 5.

The results of accuracy studies met the acceptance criteria, with the average recovery from each concentration level falling within the range of 98.0%–102.0% and a total average recovery of 100.4%.

Table 5. Accuracy of PVP 30.

Level of concentration	Average % Recovery
70% (1.75 mg/mL, n = 3)	99.7 ± 0.21
100% (2.50 mg/mL, n = 3)	100.7 ± 0.35
130% (3.25 mg/mL, n = 3)	100.9 ± 0.29

Precision

The method's repeatability was evaluated through six determinations at 100% of the test concentration. Intermediate precision was investigated using authentic homoge-

neous samples, performed on three days by three analysts. The percentage of relative standard deviation (% RSD) was calculated to determine the method's precision. The results are presented in Tables 6, 7.

Table 6. Repeatability results.

Replicate	% Assay of PVP
1	101.0
2	100.7
3	100.3
4	100.6
5	100.1
6	100.4
Mean	100.5
% RSD	0.34

Table 7. Intermediate precision results.

Replicate	Assay of PVP 30 as % Label Claim		
	Day 1/Analyst 1	Day 2/Analyst 2	Day 3/Analyst 3
1	96.5	98.7	95.1
2	96.1	94.8	95.0
3	96.1	97.5	96.6
4	96.0	97.6	94.8
5	96.5	95.7	97.0
6	96.1	97.6	95.1
Mean	96.2	97.0	95.6
%RSD	0.22	1.50	0.98

Figure 5. Calibration plot of PVP 30 standard solution.

The precision testing results were within the acceptance criteria of % RSD, which was not more than 2.0%. Moreover, the results of the accuracy and precision studies indicated that the method operates accurately and precisely within acceptable parameters.

Robustness

The robustness of an analytical procedure is a measure of its capacity to meet the expected performance criteria during normal use. Robustness is tested by deliberate variations of analytical procedure parameters (Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use 2022). The robustness test used varying column temperature, flow rate, and mobile phase composition. The column temperature was varied at 20 °C, 30 °C, and 40 °C. The flow rate of the mobile phase was varied at 0.5 mL/min, 0.6 mL/min, and 0.7 mL/min.

Meanwhile, the mobile phase composition of 0.1M sodium nitrate and acetonitrile was varied at compositions of 85:15, 80:20, and 90:10. Evaluation was carried out on system suitability parameters and % recovery for each variation. The variation in column temperature, flow rate, and mobile phase composition had little effect on chromatogram quality parameters such as retention time, resolution, and theoretical number of plates, as mentioned in Table 6. % RSD area and % recovery were within limits. As a result, the proposed method can be used for quantitative analysis of PVP 30 in tablet formulations containing metformin HCl and pioglitazone HCl.

Stability of solution

The stability of standard and sample solutions was assessed to ensure their stability during analysis. Testing was conducted at room temperature (below 30 °C) over 72 hours, with observations made at 0, 24, 48, and 72 hours. The standard PVP-30, 100% accuracy, and Pio-Mix tablet sample solutions were prepared and analyzed at specified intervals. Results showed that all solutions remained stable throughout the testing period, with deviations in peak response and PVP-30 content less than 2.0%. This indicates that standard and sample solutions can be stored at room temperature for 72 hours without significant degradation. The results are presented in Table 9.

Based on the comparison of the suitability parameters with the ICH Q2(R2) guideline range for these parameters, it is shown that the method is suitable for the analysis of PVP in tablet formulations.

Table 8. Robustness study of the chromatographic system for the determination of PVP 30 by the proposed method.

Parameter	Column temperature			Flow rate			Mobile phase composition (0.1M sodium nitrate: acetonitrile)		
	20 °C	30 °C	40 °C	0.5 mL/minutes	0.6 mL/minutes	0.7 mL/minutes	(85:15)	(80:20)	(90:10)
Retention time (t_R) (minutes)	9.219 ± 0.001	9.211 ± 0.001	9.192 ± 0.002	11.065 ± 0.003	9.219 ± 0.002	7.903 ± 0.001	9.278 ± 0.001	9.207 ± 0.001	9.349 ± 0.003
Tailing factor (T)	1.42	1.43	1.46	1.43	1.43	1.44	1.45	1.42	1.50
Resolution (Rs)	7.1	7.0	6.6	7.2	7.0	7.0	6.9	6.8	6.9
No. of theoretical plates (N)	5037	4967	4576	5252	4995	4763	4998	4998	4776
% RSD of peak responses	0.10	0.06	0.09	0.13	0.10	0.15	0.07	0.22	0.15
% Recovery (n = 6)	100.4 ± 0.45	100.2 ± 0.42	99.6 ± 0.42	99.6 ± 0.40	99.4 ± 0.44	100.1 ± 0.52	99.7 ± 0.43	100.0 ± 0.49	100.4 ± 0.61

Table 9. Stability of PVP standard and sample solutions.

Time (hour)	Response area			% Recovery	
	Standard Solution	Accuracy Solution	Tablet Solution	Accuracy Solution	Tablet Solution
0	759,153	753,866	639,880	101.0	3.91
24	751,163	746,026	633,616	99.7	3.87
48	752,731	756,252	647,307	101.7	3.98
72	766,357	759,136	649,534	101.2	3.96
Average	757,351	753,820	642,584	100.9	3.93
SD	6,928	5,625	7,265	0.84	0.05
% RSD	0.91	0.75	1.13	0.83	1.21

^a% Recovery to freshly prepared standard solution

Pharmaceutical application

The validated method was subsequently applied to determine PVP content in two different pharmaceutical formulations: PioMix tablets produced in the R&D laboratory of PT. Kalbe Farma and ActMet tablets are commercially available. PVP 30 was detected at its designated retention time. The findings were presented as a percentage of the tablet weight, as detailed in Table 11.

Povidone, or PVP, is a binder in wet granulation and is generally used as a solution. Although use levels in

Table 10. Comparison of suitability parameters with the relevant ICH ranges.

Performance characteristic	Validation study methodology for assay using HPLC separation techniques, ICH Q2(R2) Guideline	Validation Result
Specificity/ Selectivity	Absence of relevant interference: With product, buffer, or appropriate matrix, and between individual peaks of interest. Spiking with known impurities/ excipients.	From the experiments performed, a complete separation of PVP 30 from the diluent and sample matrix was obtained, as shown in Fig. 4. The PVP peak has a clear baseline separation and is well separated from other components in the placebo.
Precision	Repeatability: Replicate measurements with 3 times 3 levels across the reportable range or 6 times at 100% level, considering peak(s) of interest Intermediate precision: e.g., different days, environmental conditions, analysts, equipment	The method's repeatability was evaluated through six determinations at 100% of the test concentration. Intermediate precision was investigated using authentic homogeneous samples, performed over three days by three analysts. The percentage of relative standard deviation (%RSD) was calculated to determine the method's precision. The %RSD for precision was 0.34%, and the %RSD for intermediate precision was 0.22%, 1.50%, and 0.98% for determinations on the 1 st , 2 nd , and 3 rd days, respectively. The results were well within the acceptable limit of %RSD, which is NMT 2.0%.
Accuracy	For Assay: Comparison with suitably characterised material (e.g., reference material).	Recovery studies were conducted using three levels of PVP concentration. Specific concentrations of PVP standard (70%, 100%, and 130%) were added to the placebo, and then their recoveries were determined. The results of accuracy studies met the acceptance criteria, with the average recovery from each concentration level falling within the range of 98.0%–102.0% and a total average recovery of 100.4%.
Reportable Range	Linearity: Dilution of the analytes of interest over the expected procedure range, at least 5 points	Linearity was determined for a standard of PVP 30 over a concentration range of 0.25 mg/mL to 3.75 mg/mL. The calibration curve was created using seven points covering seven different concentration levels within the specified range. The calibration curve was linear, with the equation $y = 307161x$ and a correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.9999, demonstrating a linear response between the concentration and the response area.
Robustness and other considerations (performed as part of analytical procedure development as per ICH Q14)	Deliberate variation of relevant parameters, e.g., Sample preparation: extraction volume, extraction time, temperature, dilution Separation parameters: column/capillary lot, mobile phase/buffer composition and pH, column/capillary temperature, flow rate, detection wavelength Stability of sample and reference material preparations.	The robustness test involved varying column temperature, flow rate, and mobile phase composition. Column temperature was varied at 20 °C, 30 °C, and 40 °C, while the flow rate of the mobile phase was adjusted to 0.5 mL/min, 0.6 mL/min, and 0.7 mL/min. Mobile phase composition, consisting of 0.1M sodium nitrate and acetonitrile, was varied at ratios of 85:15, 80:20, and 90:10. These variations had minimal effect on chromatogram quality parameters such as retention time, resolution, and theoretical number of plates. Both standard and sample solutions remained stable for 72 hours when stored at room temperature below 30 °C, with no significant degradation.

Table 11. Determination of PVP 30 in pharmaceutical tablets using the validated method.

	^a Mean % Recovery ± SD	% RSD
PioMix Tablet (n = 3)	3.91 ± 0.002	0.06
ActMet Tablet (n = 3)	4.12 ± 0.010	0.24

^aMean % Recovery ± SD for three determinations

the literature are reported as 2% to 5%, higher levels of up to 10% may have to be used in challenging, poorly compactable formulation (Handbook of Pharmaceutical Granulation Technology 2021). The obtained PVP 30 content was 3.91% and 4.12% by weight for PioMix and ActMet tablets, respectively.

The novelty of the optimized methodology lies in the absence of a specific established method for determining the type and quantity of PVP in tablets containing metformin HCl and pioglitazone HCl. The advantages of the optimized method include its ability to quantify a wide range of PVP concentrations with simple preparation and reliable accuracy and precision. However, a disadvantage of the method is its lengthy runtime per injection, approximately 30 minutes per injection.

Conclusion

The analysis method for PVP in tablets containing metformin HCl and pioglitazone HCl was optimized and validated using size exclusion chromatography (SEC). The HPLC system utilized an Ultrahydrogel 120 Å column with a mobile phase of 0.1 M Sodium nitrate: Acetonitrile (80:20) run isocratically. The method met the acceptance criteria for system suitability, specificity, linearity, detection & quantification limits, precision, accuracy, and robustness. The LOD and LOQ were 0.0355 mg/mL and 0.1075 mg/mL, respectively. Stability tests showed that standard and sample solutions remained stable for 72 hours at room temperature (below 30 °C). The method was robust against intentional changes in column tem-

perature, flow rate, and mobile phase composition. PVP 30 content in PioMix and ActMet tablets was 3.91% and 4.12%, respectively.

Author contributions

All authors participated in the conception and design of the study. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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